

Developing a Postpartum Hypertension and Preeclampsia Nurse Education Program

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Background

- Postpartum hypertension & preeclampsia increases obstetrical readmissions
- In the US in the last 20 years, readmissions increased by 25%
- The Joint Commission issued two mandated perinatal standards:
 - 1st focus was maternal hemorrhage
 - 2nd focus was postpartum hypertension preeclampsia
- Mortality: 63,000 deaths annually
- The two standards were not implemented at the project site

Purpose Statement

- Developed, implemented, & evaluated a nurse education program on postpartum hypertension & preeclampsia
- AIMS
- Examined changes in nurses' knowledge about postpartum hypertension & preeclampsia & self efficacy regarding use of evidence-based practices & the new JC standards
- Assessed readmission rates before and after implementing the educational intervention
- Identified the extent to which patients received the education
- Developed an education protocol

Methods

- Design: Pretest Post test
- Setting: Postpartum unit at a public hospital in Southern California
- Sample: Postpartum Nurses (N=27):
- Data Collection: March 2021-April 2021
- Measures:
 - Postpartum Knowledge Teaching Survey
 - Demographics:
 - Self evaluation questions.
 - Evidence Base Self Efficacy Scale
 - Readmission rates using T-chart

Integration of IOWA Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Results

- Days between readmissions increased after training, but not enough data points to reflect significance
- Post training, more nurses improved confidence in using evidence base practice
- Post training, more nurses improved understanding of postpartum complications and discussion of complications
- Post training, more nurses believed it was their responsibility to discuss complications

Discussion

- 33% of participants were not aware of the new JC perinatal standards
- 70% of participants were not aware that maternal mortality and morbidity had increased
- It is the goal of this project that the nursing education program will be implemented to enhance the quality of care for postpartum patients
- The project will help improve the care of postpartum patients

Clinical Implications

- Implement standardized nurse education program
- Adherence to Joint Commission updated standards to improve patient quality of care
- Decrease time between readmissions with the diagnosis postpartum hypertension preeclampsia
- Reduce maternal morbidity and mortality

Conclusions

- The new JC perinatal standard needs to be incorporated into nurse's education plan
- All postpartum patients need to be taught about postpartum hypertension/preeclampsia upon admission, throughout their stay, and on the day of discharge
- By providing a postpartum hypertension protocol, it will ensure that all patients will receive the same education

Recommendations

- Sustain the project at the project facility.
- Replicate the project at my own facility.
- Include the nursing education program for all new hires and include the education in the nursing annual competency training.